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Global Dynamics

in Responsible Research

A two-day Virtual Symposium hosted by
The Einstein Foundation

DFG Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft

Wissenschaftliches Publizieren als Grundlage und Gestaltungsfeld der Wissenschaftsbewertung

Open Science als Teil der Wissenschaftskultur

Positionierung der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft

MAKING FAIRER ASSESSMENTS POSSIBLE

RECOMMENDATION ON RESEARCH ASSESSMENT PROCESSES

Open Science in university approaches to academic

A Pathway towards Multidimensional Academic Careers

A LERU Framework for the Assessment of Researchers

Prof. Bert Overlaet

LERU position paper January 2022

Guidelines for Good Evaluation Practice with the ACUMEN Portfolio

Statement by three national academies (Académie des Sciences, Leopoldina and Royal Society) on good practice in the evaluation of researchers and research projects

eua EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY ASSOCIATION

ACTION PLAN FOR DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS MARCH 2022

G7 Research Compact

Room for everyone's talent

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science

The European University Association and Science Europe Join Efforts to Improve Scholarly Research Assessment Methodologies

16 May 2022

Towards a reform of the research assessment system

ARBEITSGEMEINSCHAFT HOCHSCHULMEDIZIN

NOR-CAM - A toolbox for recognition and rewards for academic careers

U|N Universität Norwegen

Open Science and Intellectual Property Rights

COARA

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

COMMENT The Leiden Manifesto for research metrics

GAO

United States Government Accountability Office Report to the Ranking Member, Committee on Commerce, Science, and Transportation, U.S. Senate

RESEARCH RELIABILITY

Federal Actions Needed to Promote Stronger Research Practices

etc.....

Logos of AWMF, Medizinischer Fakultätensystem, marburger bund, dgmr, bvmf, Deutscher Hochschulverband, HRK

Wissenschaftsadäquate Kriterien zur Messung der Forschungsleistungen

- But **underrepresented** in this discussion: Topics related to decolonization of knowledge, representation of research from local communities in non-WEIRD countries, multilingualism in Open Science and how Open Science, if done wrong, will compound inequities.
- ECR Symposium organized by international ECRs (eLife Community Ambassadors)
- To provide a platform for the perspectives of early career researchers who will define the future research culture and incentives that drive researchers' behaviours.

Ulrich Dirnagl
Secretary Einstein Foundation Award, Director
BIH Quest Center, Director Experimental
Neurology Charité-Universitätsmedizin

- Symposium **supported** by:

- Linked to **Einstein Foundation Award** for Promoting Quality in Research

- Individual (€200 k, institutional €200k, ECR award €100k)
- **Thanks to:** eLife Ambassador program: Ailís O'Carroll, and Verena Heise, Ulrike Pannasch, and the ECRs... in particular Batool

Our mission - to help scientists *accelerate discovery* by operating a platform for research communication that encourages and recognises *the most responsible behaviours in science*

128 eLife Community Ambassadors from all over the globe
50+ countries,
20+ research disciplines,
120+ different universities, institutes, labs and research communities represented.

Global Dynamics of Responsible Research

eLIFE Community
Ambassadors

Meet the Organisers

Verena Haage

Postdoctoral fellow at the Center for Translational and Computational Neuroimmunology at Columbia University

Batool Almarzouq

Computational biologist affiliated with the University of Liverpool in the UK and KAIMRC in Saudi Arabia

Samuel Eziuzor

Postdoc at the Applied Microbial Systems Ecology Lab of the School of Engineering, University of British Columbia

Renato Augusto Corrêa dos Santos

Post-doctoral researcher in the field of bioenergy in the Computational, Evolutionary and Systems Biology Lab

Nalaka Wijekoon

Neuroscientist affiliated with the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Maastricht University

Lamis Yahia Mohamed Elkheir

Pharmaceutical chemistry lecturer at the faculty of Pharmacy in the University of Khartoum

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<https://symposium.einsteinfoundation.de>

creative
commons

*“We are all water from different rivers
That’s why it’s so easy to meet
We’re all water in this vast, vast ocean
Someday we will evaporate together”*

- Yoko Ono, Japanese multimedia artist, singer, songwriter,
and peace activist

PLANT THE SEEDS

Paint a better picture of the global perspectives around responsible research

HIGHLIGHT PROBLEMS

Highlight problems hindering the global implementation of responsible research but also try and bring potential solutions

FUTURE OF RESEARCH CULTURE

Project the future of research culture that we are hoping to attain as ECRs, where no one is left behind

Keynote Speakers

Leslie Chan

*Knowledge Equity and Socially Responsible
Research*

Joy Owango

*Democratizing research through open
access*

Paz Míguez & Laurel Ascenzi

*Co-creating and Teaching Open Science
from the Global South*

Tatsuya Amano

*Is non-English-language literature
important in science?*

Emmy Tsang

Open infrastructure for whom?

Workshops

Anne Lee Steele, Melissa Black

*Exploring the Internationalisation and
localisation for Open Science through the
Turing Way*

Kate Hertweck

*Open science beyond research scientists,
Hands-on Workshop*

Manifesto

ECR Perspective around the Global Dynamics of **Open Science**

- **Decolonization** of knowledge
- Representation of research from local communities in **non-WEIRD countries**
- **Multilingualism** in Open Science
- How Open Science, if done wrong, will compound **inequities**

Housekeeping

- All sessions will be recorded except for discussion and workshops
- Reminder: **Code of conduct**
<https://symposium.einsteinfoundation.de/CoC.html>
 - If you experience or witness unacceptable behaviour, or have any other concerns, please report it by contacting the code of conduct committee.
- If you need a **certificate of attendance**, please add your name and contact in this etherpad: https://pad.sfconservancy.org/p/certificate_day1
- We are using **Otter.ai** for transcription.
 - Otter.ai transcript to follow along by clicking on "live on otter.ai" on top right of your screen

